

PRINCIPLES OF ACCOUNTING – QUICK CASES

UNIT 2: ETHICAL CASE 1. CLIMATE AND SUSTAINABILITY

Authors: Nadia Gulko, University of Lincoln, Karen McBride, University of Portsmouth, Nick McGuigan, Monash University.

CASE OUTLINE

If we do not protect our nature. We cannot protect ourselves. Climate change refers to long-term shifts in temperatures and weather patterns. Human activities have been the main driver of climate change, primarily due to the burning of fossil fuels like coal, oil and gas. Climate change is greater than any one of us, but it requires every single one of us to come together to ensure there can and will be a future for the next generations to come.

This case allows you to reflect on the history and long-term implications after two natural disasters:

A) the BP Deepwater Horizon the Gulf of Mexico explosion 2010 as the largest spill of oil in the history of marine oil drilling operations; and

B) the Yasuní-ITT initiative 2007 that highlights the environmental and social impacts of oil extraction in the Yasuní National Park in Ecuador which is a United Nations Biosphere Reserve and home to some of the planet's last Indigenous peoples living in voluntary isolation.

Briefly review the following case resources and answer/discuss questions

CASE RESOURCES:

1. Climate Change - a Short Film

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jAa58N4Jlos>

2. What Is Climate Change? United Nations

<https://www.un.org/en/climatechange/what-is-climate-change>

3. BP's record criminal fine

<http://www.bbc.com/news/business-20336898>

4. Oil Spill: 100 Days, 100 Photos

<https://www.cbsnews.com/pictures/oil-spill-100-days-100-photos/>

5. British Petroleum Oil Spill in the Gulf of Mexico

https://da0854d1-c956-4b5c-a58c-cd1c1f129a5f.usfiles.com/ugd/da0854_a002d77555c94bb2802e6dd5955a23b0.pdf

6. A deep dive into BP's Deepwater Horizon Spill

<https://www.aboutresilience.com/a-deep-dive-into-bps-deepwater-horizon-spill-a-case-study/>

7. BP settles Deepwater Horizon oil spill claims

<https://www.cbsnews.com/news/bp-settles-deepwater-horizon-oil-spill-in-gulf-of-mexico-for-20-billion/>

8. They cleaned up BP's massive oil spill. Now they're sick – and want justice (2023)

<https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2023/apr/20/bp-oil-spill-deepwater-horizon-health-lawsuits>

9. The Yasuní ITT Case

<https://www.rightsofnaturetribunal.org/cases/yasuni-itt-case/>

10. Yasuní: The significance of a victory. The Ecuadorian people's decision to stop oil extraction in the Yasuní National Park now brings new challenges.

<https://www.wrm.org.uy/bulletin-articles/yasuni-the-significance-of-a-victory>

CASE QUESTIONS AND DISCUSSION

1. What is the significance of safety and ethical risks in the BP Deepwater Horizon and Yasuní-ITT cases?
2. How can ethical leadership help organisations to manage risk?
3. What are the ethical and long-term implications of cases like these?
4. What are the similarities between these two cases?
5. Identify which SDGs do the BP Deepwater Horizon and Yasuní-ITT cases relate to?
6. What would you do to prevent cases like this happening again?